

The Cacaxtla Gran Basamento

also known as "The Cacaxtla Acropolis"

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Entry tags: Mesoamerican Religions, Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley, Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla, Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Cacaxtla Religion, Mayan, Mesoamerica, Language, Religious Place, Basin of Mexico

The Cacaxtla archaeological site, located in Tlaxcala, Mexico, stands as a compelling archaeological testament from the Epiclassic period (650-950 AD). This elevated complex, is strategically positioned to oversee fertile plains at the South and surrounded by the Sierra Nevada and the Popocatepetl volcano on the West, and the Malinche Volcano at North. The Acropolis, also called Great Basement, is one of the three settlements that configures the Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla prehispanic city. While public monuments and temples were built 500 meters at the West of the Acropolis, commoner settlements were on the hills of present-day village of Nativitas. Of particular interest are the manifestation of elite occupations in the architectural layout and iconography of the site. The expansive palace-like structures, ceremonial courtyards, and elaborate murals collectively signify the presence of a ruling class exercising both political and religious authority. The mural compositions, depicting individuals adorned in regalia engaged in ceremonial and warfare activities, accentuate the elite nature of the Acropolis. But they also demonstrate how strategic this place was after Teotihuacan's fall and decline, as it became a trading and ideological center where goods, people, and ideologies converged from other parts of ancient Mesoamerica.

Date Range: 650 CE - 950 CE

Region: Xochitecal-Cacaxtlia

Region tags: Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley, Complejo de Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla-Atlachino, Mesoamerica, Mexico

Archaeological Area of Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla, Tlaxcala, Mexico, during Epiclassic period.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: García Cook, Ángel & Leonor Merino Carrión (comps.). *Antología de Tlaxcala*. 4 vols. Colección Antología, I-II-III, & IV. Mexico City, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, 1997
- Source 2: Serra Puche, Mari Carmen & Jesús Carlos Lazcano Arce. *Xochitécatl-Cacaxtla. Cronología de su exploración*. *Arqueología mexicana*, (XIX)117, 36-37, Mexico City, 2012
- Source 3: Piña Chan, Román. *Cacaxtla : fuentes históricas y pinturas*. Mexico, Fondo de cultura económica, 2005

- Source 1: Martin, Simon. El Templo Rojo y los mayas: arte, mitología y contactos culturales en las pinturas de Cacaxtla. *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México Volumen V: Cacaxtla. Estudios, Tomo III.* Edited by Maria Teresa Uriarte Castañeda, 529-545. Mexico, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2015
- Source 2: Dominguez, Elba & Javier Urcid. El ascenso al poder del señor 4 Perro: las pinturas murales del Conjunto 2-sub en Cacaxtla, 547-607. Mexico, *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México Volumen V: Cacaxtla. Estudios, Tomo III.* Edited by Maria Teresa Uriarte Castañeda. Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2015
- Source 3: Urcid, Javier & Elba Dominguez. La Casa de la Tierra, la Casa del Cielo: los murales en el Edificio A de Cacaxtla. *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México Volumen V: Cacaxtla. Estudios, Tomo III.* Edited by Maria Teresa Uriarte Castañeda, 609-675. Mexico, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2015
- Source 1: Uriarte Castañeda, María Teresa & Erik Velázquez García. El mural de la Batalla de Cacaxtla. Nuevas aproximaciones. *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México Volumen V: Cacaxtla. Estudios, Tomo III.* Edited by Maria Teresa Uriarte Castañeda, 677-739. Mexico, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2015.
- Source 2: Lucet, Geneviève. Arquitectura Cacaxtla, lectura del espacio. *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México Volumen V: Cacaxtla. Estudios, Tomo II.* Edited by Maria Teresa Uriarte Castañeda, 43-109. Mexico, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2013.
- Source 3: Helmke, Christophe & Jesper Nielsen. La iconografía de Cacaxtla bajo la influencia maya: identidad, procedencia y datación. *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México Volumen V: Cacaxtla. Estudios, Tomo II,* 363-381. Edited by Maria Teresa Uriarte Castañeda. Mexico, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2013

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.inah.gob.mx/zonas/zona-arqueologica-de-cacaxtla-xochitecatl>
- Source 1 Description: Zona arqueológica de Cacaxtla-Xochitecatl, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia
- Source 2 URL: <https://lugares.inah.gob.mx/es/zonas-arqueologicas/zonas/1866-cacaxtla-xochitecatl.html>
- Source 2 Description: Lugares INAH Cacaxtla-Xochitécatl
- Source 3 URL: <https://doi.org/10.22201/ie.18703062e.2014.104.2516>
- Source 3 Description: Brittenham, Claudia and Debra Nagao. Cacaxtla Figural Ceramics, *Anales de Investigaciones Estéticas* 1(104)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: 1972-2024

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: Proyecto arqueológico Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation
– Other [specify]: Volcanoes

Notes: Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla is situated the Popocatepetl and Iztaccihuatl on the West and La Malinche at the East. Xochitecatl, Cacaxtla and Natavitas are respectively build on a natural hill.

– Water source

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Other [specify]: On the Western part of the site flows the Atoyac river. On the Eastern part is the Zahuapan river. At the North was the Rosario lake that has been dried up since 1886.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Terracing
– Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Acropolis is the middle structure of three. At the south lies Xochitecatl, dedicated to public activities such as trade and religion. The eastern part, Nativitas was inhabited by commoners.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Political

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla was abandoned at the end of the 10th century CE.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: The Acropolis counts with 9 stages of construction. Every single stage was fully refilled with stones, so that some former stages were conserved. Some sections were closed with walls and refilled.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The reactive here is inappropriate for this context. Archaeology excavations have been followed by restoration and conservation works.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: According to ceramics and wall painting, Mesoamerican deities like Tlaloc, Quetzalcóatl or Venus impersonators may have been worshipped.

Notes: Brittenham and Nagao (2014) pointed out that the eleven clay sculptures called Lords of Cacaxtla had Tlaloc attributes. They may have put on the roof of a building as architectural ornaments.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

– Other [specify]: Elite members

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Corvee labourers

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Even if the site has been occupied since Preclassic period, the position of Cacaxtla between Mexico valley and the Gulf Coast was essential for goods and material trading.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: It is thought that the three sectors of the site may be a representation of the surrounding sierra.

Reference: Brittenham, Claudia, and Debra Nagao. "Cacaxtla Figural Ceramics". *Anales Del Instituto De Investigaciones Estéticas* XXXVI, no. 104 (2014): 55–96.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.22201/iie.18703062e.2014.104.2516>.

Reference: Serra Puche, Mari Carmen, and Jesús Carlos Lazcano Arce. *Vida cotidiana xochitecatl-cacaxtla. días, años, milenios*. 1st ed.. Ciudad de México: Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2011.

<http://bdjc.ia.unam.mx/items/show/134#lg=1&slide=0>.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Acropolis was made of multiple-room palaces and porticoes whose entrances were facing open patios. Storage facilities and production have also been detected. All these structures were related by stairs and narrow corridors.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: See the notes for the former reactive.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 22000

Notes: The Acropolis has a rectangular shape with the following measures: 200 m long for 110 m wide. The Superior platform has a 9880 square meters surface.

Reference: Lucet, Geneviève. "Arquitectura De Cacaxtla, Lectura Del Espacio". In *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México V Cacaxtla Tomo II Estudios*, edited by María Teresa Uriarte Castañeda and María Fernanda Salazar Gil, 19-109. Mexico City: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2013.

<http://www.ebooks.esteticas.unam.mx/items/show/37>.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 120

Notes: The Acropolis has been constructed in several phases, so its height has evolved according to the new build stage. (Lucet 2013, 22)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 2.7

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

Notes: Sand was used to prepare lime and stucco.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Wood was little used. But its presence helped with the datation of the site. A wood dintel was dated between 556 and 835 CE, allowing the Mural of the Great Battle to be done around 655 CE.

Reference: Serra Puche, Mari Carmen, and Jesús Carlos Lazcano Arce. *Vida cotidiana xochitecatl-cacaxtla. días, años, milenios*. 1st ed.. Ciudad de México: Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2011.
<http://bdjc.iaa.unam.mx/items/show/134#lg=1&slide=0>.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Stone was used to build the walls and to fill the gaps previously to a new phase building.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The entire Acropolis was stuccoed, meaning that every building was covered with white stuccoed, then eventually painted with red cenefas.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Buildings were all stuccoed in the inside. A lot of them had red drip caps. Wall paintings were also very common but not generalized.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: The Red Temple, the A Building, the E Building, the Venus Temple contain figural decoration.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Feathered Serpent is one example of the deities depicted in Cacaxtla. It can be seen in the Red Temple stair and corridor, as well in the Building A wall paintings.

Reference: Brittenham, Claudia . The murals of cacaxtla: the power of painting in ancient central Mexico. Austin: University of Texas Press, 2015.

Reference: Lucet, Geneviève. "MEASUREMENT IN CACAXTLA: A MULTICULTURAL AND SYMBOLIC CONVERGENCE" 32, no. 2 (January 9, 2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0956536119000282>.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: In Building A, feathered serpent's counterparts is the jaguar-serpent.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The painted walls of the Battle, of the merchant with its basket at the Red Temple, or the Eagle and Jaguars warriors are examples of humans depicted in the

Acropolis of Cacaxtla.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A quetzal bird is painted in the south wall of Building B. In the Red Temple stairs, frogs, shells, crabs are depicted in the flowing water below the Feathered Serpent body.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Temple of Venus has two pilasters painted with a scorpion-tail man.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The Celosia is an example of a geometrical architectural feature. It was stuccoed.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Helmke and Jensen published several studies about the writing system used at Cacaxtla. Most are calendar dates.

Reference: Helmke, Christophe, and Jesper Nielsen. *The Writing System of Cacaxtla, Tlaxcala, Mexico*. Ancient America Special Publication Number Two. Barnardsville: Boundary End Archaeology Research Center, 2011.

Reference: Helmke, Christophe, and Jesper Nielsen. "La Escritura Jeroglífica De Cacaxtla". In *La Pintura Mural Prehispánica En México V Cacaxtla Tomo II Estudios*, 383-425. Mexico City: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2013. <http://www.ebooks.esteticas.unam.mx/items/show/37>.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Plants motifs

Notes: On the Red Temple stairways wall-paintings, corn and cacao plants are depicted with human head features.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: The Red Temple corridor with the Feathered Serpents painting were hidden and filled in order to build the stair that would lead to a patio. But it is important to remind that Cacaxtla has been amplified and rebuilt several times.

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: However, main part of the decoration is available to the viewer. It consists in red painted cenefa and elaborated wall paintings. They contain floral, animal, anthropomorphic and calendar features.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: See the feline sculpture shown above. Eleven ceramics anthropomorphic sculptures have been found around the Acropolis and another one was found during 1981 excavations at site. Brittenham and Nagao present them as the Eleven Lords of Cacaxtla. They might have been used as roof ornaments.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: anthropomorphic features

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Secco

Notes: Magaloni Kerpel (1998) and Magaloni Kerpel, Brittenham, Baglioni, Giorgi and Bernini (2013) described the process of preparation of the walls before being painted with mineral and vegetal pigments. About the painters of Cacaxtla, we recommend reading Brittenham book chapter (2013).

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Feathered Serpent was of the deities represented on the wall of Temple A or in the Red Temple stairs. We can infer that the elite of Cacaxtla did worship some deities already present at Teotihuacan and in the Mayan region, due to the influence of this region in Cacaxtla iconography.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: In Building A, the feathered serpent is facing the jaguar serpent, representing the opposition between solar/sky and moon/cthonian motives. Observing carefully the Red Temple stairs,

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The Mural of the Battle has been interpreted as the fight between Mayan incomers against autochthonous people of the center of Mexico. How McCafferty and McCafferty proposed that two main characters on the Wall of the Battle are actually women. As a matter of fact, the painting may depict the capture of a founding queen of Cacaxtla.

Reference: McCafferty, Sharisse D., and Geoffrey G. McCafferty. "The Conquered Women of Cacaxtla" 5, no. 2 (1994). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0956536100001127>.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Calendar and names dates were painted on the painted wall of the Battle and on the walls of the Building A.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Such as feathered-serpents, jaguar-serpents, jaguar-tortoises.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Clay moldings reliefs around the main door of the Building A suggest that Earth representations were prepared in the Mayan way.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The Temple of Venus has a blue body painted man and woman with a star belt. The male figure also had a scorpion tail. On the Red Temple stairs, two rotting corpses were depicted, along with calendar dates.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: On the Red Temple stairs, two rotting corpses were depicted, along with calendar dates.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: The Mural of the Battle shows two factions fighting. On the Building B, the male individuals depicted wearing jaguar and bird garments.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: For some scholar, the Mural of the Battle represents a cosmic war. Considering the Building A walls, Graulich considers that the characters depicted with jaguar and avian garments represent the cycle of day and night, as they may also represent the ruling system in Cacaxtla.

Reference: Graulich, Michel. "Dualities in Cacaxtla". In *Mesoamerican Dualism*. 46th International Congress of Americanists, Amsterdam 1988., edited by Rudolf van Zantwijk and Rob de Ridder. Utrecht: RUU-ISOR, 1990.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: To Urcid and Dominguez (2013), the painted wall of Substructure 2, including the Red Temple, may represent how the ruler 2 Dog became a ruler of Cacaxtla.

Reference: Dominguez, Elba, and Javier Urcid. "El ascenso al poder del señor 4 perro: las pinturas murales de conjunto 2-sub de cacaxtla". In *La pintura mural prehispánica en México V cacaxtla tomo III estudios*, edited by María Teresa Uriarte and María Fernanda Salazar Gil, 547–607. Mexico City: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2013. <http://www.ebooks.esteticas.unam.mx/items/show/38>.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Phytomorphic features were also important at Cacaxtla. Michener (2013) suggests that cocoa and maize plants are represented in different stages of their growth.

Reference: Michener, David. "Las plantas en cacaxtla: una perspectiva botánica". In *La pintura mural prehispánica en México V cacaxtla tomo III estudios*, edited by María Teresa Uriarte Castañeda and María Fernanda Salazar Gil, 517-27. Mexico City: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Estéticas, 2013.
<http://www.ebooks.esteticas.unam.mx/items/show/38>.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Field doesn't know

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other

–Yes [specify]: bowls, plates among others

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Mesoamerican religious tradition wasn't monotheist. The Acropolis wasn't the place of cult. Xochitecatl was the precinct where temples and shrines were probably used for the cult of several deities. However, the ceramic features called the "Eleven Lords of Cacaxtla" do have features of Postclassic nahua gods like Xipe Totec and Tlaloc.

Reference: Brittenham, Claudia, and Debra Nagao. "Cacaxtla Figural Ceramics". *Anales Del Instituto De Investigaciones Estéticas* XXXVI, no. 104 (2014): 55-96.

- ↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they unquestionably good:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they other:
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Nonhuman entities can affect human beings and animals directly. The presence of the feathered serpent and the jaguar serpent seems to influence directly the two main characters of the Building A paintings.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Libations:

–Yes [specify]: Blood or pulque

Notes: This is a conjecture according to libations observed in archaeological sites of the Mesoamerican religious tradition.

Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: In Classic Maya and Postclassic daily diet, corn tamales, turkey, beans and squash dishes, etc. seems to have been prepared for the deities.

Notes: About ritual Mesoamerican dishes, consult the works of Mazzetto.

Reference: Mazzetto, Elena, and Natalia Moragas Segura. "Contexts of Offerings and Ritual Maize in the Pictographic Record in Central Mexico" 26 (April 13, 2015).
<https://doi.org/10.30674/scripta.67448>.

Reference: Mazzetto, Elena. "La Comida Ritual En Las Fiestas De Las Veintenas Mexicanas : Un Acercamiento a Su Tipología Y Simbolismo", no. 25 (July 9, 2013).
<https://doi.org/10.4000/alhim.4461>.

Animal sacrifice:

–Yes [specify]: quails, turkey might have been sacrificed.

Human sacrifice:

–Yes [specify]: As a part of the Mesoamerican religious tradition.

Sacred objects:

–Yes [specify]: Clay urns, clay figurines, Incensers, sculptures

Notes: Among these sacred artefacts are the sculptures of the Eleven Lords, conserved and shown at the Cacaxtla site museum. These clay sculptures represented deities known during the Posclassic era as Xipe Totec and Tlaloc. These images were looted and conserved at a particular's home in Nativitas. A fragmentary exemplar was found in situ during the Acropolis excavations.

Reference: Brittenham, Claudia, and Debra Nagao. "Cacaxtla Figural Ceramics". *Anales Del Instituto De Investigaciones Estéticas* XXXVI, no. 104 (2014): 55–96.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.22201/ije.18703062e.2014.104.2516>.

Daily life objects:

–Yes [specify]: Obsidian and flint knives, clay seals, scrapers, clay bowls and plates.

Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - No
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes

- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: There is no number known.
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Periodicity is unknown
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Adults
 - Yes

- ↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:
 - Male
 - Female

↳ Children
– Field doesn't know

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves
– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:
– Male
– Female

↳ Elites
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳

By all the community

– No

↳

By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Sacrifices were assisted by the elite.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's highly probable if we compare Cacaxtla with other sites and cultures. However, it's hard to tell which living space at Cacaxtla was inhabited by religious specialists.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: At least a part of the Acropolis could have been used for such activity.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As a highly hierarchized society, Xochitecatl-Cacaxtla was ruling surrounding territories that have to pay tribute.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Several storage rooms and units known as cuexcomate have been discovered in the different stages of construction (Alvarado & al. 2011)

Reference: Alvarado León, Claudia , Silvia Garza Tarazona, Norberto González Crespo, and Beatriz Palavicini. "Almacenamiento En Dos Sitios Del Epiclásico: Xochicalco (morelos) Y

Cacaxtla (tlaxcala)". Mexico: Centro de estudios mexicanos y centroamericanos, 2012.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.4000/books.cemca.9112>.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Function for water management:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: The site was surrounded by two rivers.

↳ Part of the transportation network:
– No
Notes: The Acropolis was enclosed by fortifications. Speaking of a direct and open access to the different levels of the Acropolis, they didn't exist. These two architectural features tell us about the militaristic society Cacaxtla might have been.

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Helmke y Nielsen (2013) explained that Cacaxtla corpus of inscriptions includes logograms. But its scripture might have been logosilabical too. Actually, Cacaxtla's writing system might have been the continuity of Teotihuacan's one. In Cacaxtla, the epigraphic corpus was mainly painted on the walls. It consisted in calendar dates, toponyms, bowl's signs, titles, &c. Mesoamerican writing systems are deeply rooted with religious activities or symbolic features.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Writing, reading and interpretations of scriptures were privileges for the elite.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

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